

A STUDY OF TEACHER STRESS AMONG SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract:

The teachers are considered to be the most powerful environment for child development. Stress can be defined as the physiological and psychological reaction with which it occurs as a consequence of perception of imbalance between the level of demand placed upon individuals and their capabilities to meet those demands. Stress relates to the causes and consequences of less than optimum performance which is attributable to motivation. Teacher stress has a nationwide concern and relatively new area of empirical factors prepared by teachers as being troublesome or stressful have included students discipline, negative attitudes towards school, physical violence, is adequate preparation time, lack of clear role definition and heavy workloads. The present study aims to study the teachers stress among school teachers. The sample was selected using random sampling techniques. The sample included 85 males and 115 females schools teachers working in Vellore district. Rama's teacher stress self-rating five-point scale developed and standardized by Dr. Krishnan Raju (1994) because it is more appropriate to measure the teacher stress and the data obtained was subjected to statistical analysis (descriptive analysis and t-test). Findings suggest that there is no significant difference between teachers stress irrespective to gender, age, educational qualification, management and teaching experience towards school teachers.

Keys Words: Teacher Stress & School Teachers

Introduction:

Teachers are the backbone of the educational process and they play a vital role in building the nation. Teachers act as a pivot around which all the educational programmers" rotate. Teachers are crucial in the implementation process also it is a fact that the quality of the teachers influence the level of achievement of students. Teachers have an impact on the completion of all the desirous outcomes envisaged in an individual by the society. Thus the role of a teacher does not limit itself to imparting knowledge alone, but in broadening the national outlook enhancing a sense of efficacy and competency among the future citizens, and preparing individuals for the right type of profession. Education is the most powerful tool and it brings effective instrument of introducing radical change in the behavior of man. The information received through sense organs while interacting with ones environment, are processed by various mental abilities like perceiving, strong, classifying, compiling, expanding, recalling etc. It has already been mentioned that education is a process by which the personality of the child is developed and this is possible by the interaction between the child and his environment. The teachers are considered to be the most powerful environment for child development. Stress can be defined as the physiological and psychological reaction with which it occurs as a consequence of perception of imbalance between the level of demand placed upon individuals and their capabilities to meet those demands. Stress relates to the causes and consequences of less than optimum performance which is attributable to motivation. Such level of motivation by its nature or its intensity is inappropriate to the work being performed, personality and abilities of the individual is concerned. People with low hardiness may have more difficulties in coping with pressure to stress. Optimism is the extent to which a person sees life in positive or negative terraces. Optimistic people handle stress better. They will be able to see the positive side of the situation and recognize that things may eventually improve.

Teacher Stress:

Job stress is most common psychological phenomena that are prevalent among people who are in different jobs and professions. The stress studies are initially directed toward industrial organizations within the private sector. To believe that stress may be especially prevalent among human service profession, particularly the teaching profession, (Kjyiacou and Sutcliffe 1977-78; Pettegrew and Wolf 1982, Cherniss 1980: and Cooper and Marshall 1978). As a teaching is a human service profession, stress within the teaching profession is considerable and may have far-reaching consequences on the entire education system. Teaching is complex process were in teacher is expected to exhibit many skills. This makes a teacher to experiences stress in the profession. Further, Pettegrew and Wolf (1982) opined that "Teacher stress has a nationwide concern and relatively new area of empirical factors prepared by teachers as being troublesome or stressful have included students discipline, negative attitudes towards school, physical violence, is adequate preparation time, lack of clear role definition and heavy workloads". (Bearly, Myette and Serma, 1983; Chichen and Koff, 1978; Olander and Ferrel, 1970).

Teacher is subjected to stress due to incoherent social life, widening social distance, segregation, lack of societal support, corruption, nepotism, unnecessary societal involvement in day-to-day activities, high degree of social indiscipline, deterioration of values, lack of social security etc.

Effects of Teacher Stress::

As job stress effect organizational performance, teacher stress impedes teacher performance in teaching. Infact it is assumed that mild stress can even enhance performance but high level of stress can create physical, Psychological and behavioral problems among teacher. There are several research studies, which observed that, a high level of stress accompanied by physical illness such as high blood pressures, ulcers and even cancer. Similarly high level of stress may be accompanied by psychological problems such as anger, anxiety, depression, nervousness, irritability, tension and boredom. Excessive stress may also result in behavioral problems such as sleeplessness, under eating or over eating, increased smoking and drinking and drug abuse. Many researches of teacher

Need for the Study:

Teachers are the real builders of the nation. They are the pillars to uphold the national aspirations of progress. The teachers' role in the growth, development and prosperity of the nation is undeniable. It is the teachers who mould the future society and influence the coming generations towards successful achievement of the national goals. If the teachers have to perform their duties with dedication and sincerity they must possess adequate mental health. Job-related stress is an important factor in teacher's motivation and retention. Two of the main sources of this stress were cited as work pressure and students' misbehavior. This stress could be putting the school teachers' health at risk, as many find themselves unable to unwind out of school. Basically, school teachers play three different roles at home, school and society.

Accomplishment of educational goals and the objectives of teaching is possible only with teachers those who are competent in teaching and free from any type of stress. Teacher stress directly or indirectly influences the competency of teachers in teaching. So the teacher who is subjected to stress may not be possible to teach properly which in term competency in teaching.

Theoretically, the teacher stress may be heard to perform teaching in a competent way. But in practice how far teacher stress is influencing on teaching competency and to what extent teacher stress and teaching competency are related-are the questions waiting for answer. Hence, this study has taken up to find out how teacher stress and teaching competency are inter-related to each other in the context of high school education.

Design is the heart of research. The selection of sample includes the sampling techniques used, the reasons for selection of a particular sampling technique and the selection of the sample according to different variables. The selection of suitable tool for collection of data and the procedure followed in administering the tool to collect the data required for the present study.

Aim of the Study:

The study was aimed to study the teacher stress among school teachers.

Sample:

The sample selected for the present investigation consist 200 teachers of different Schools in Vellore District, Tamil nadu. Both male and female teachers are found in the sample. The age of the teachers below 35 and above 35 years, Teachers of two cadres of P.G. and graduate teachers. Teachers having 2 slabs experience i.e. above 15 years, below 15 years are found in the sample. Another sample Government teacher and private teachers.

Tool:

In the present study, the investigator adopted the Rama's teacher stress self-rating five-point scale developed and standardized by. Dr. Krishnan Raju (1994) because it is more appropriate to measure the teacher stress.

Description of the Tool:

In the present study, the investigator adopted the Rama's teacher stress self-rating five-point scale developed and standardized by. Dr. Krishnan Raju (1994) because it is more appropriate to measure the teacher stress. The responses are scored in stress according to key, for all the items scores from five to one for the five responses i.e. N. S. (No stress), Mi. S (Mild stress), Mo. S (Moderate Stress), M. S.(More Stress), S. S. (Sevier Stress) total No. of items 46 in teacher stress scale. The responses are scored according to the key. The scoring procedure, which is followed to this teacher stress also. Total number of items is 46. The maximum is 230 and the minimum possible score is 46 the high score indicates high teacher stress; the low score indicates low teacher stress.

Methodology:

The present investigation is meant to study the teacher stress of school teachers from Vellore district. Normative survey method was adopted for the conduct of the present study. The sample consisted of 200 school teachers randomly selected from Vellore district in Tamilnadu.

Objectives:

- ✓ To study the difference if any, in teacher stress of school teachers regard to gender.

- ✓ To study the difference if any, in teacher stress of school teachers regard to age.
- ✓ To study the difference if any, in teacher stress of school teachers regard to qualification.
- ✓ To study the difference if any, in teacher stress of school teachers regard to management.
- ✓ To study the difference if any, in teacher stress of school teachers regard to teaching experience.

Hypotheses:

- ✓ There is no significant difference between Male and Female school teachers towards teacher stress.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between Above 35 year’s age of school teachers and Below 35 year’s age of school teacher towards teacher stress.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between Graduate teachers and post Graduate Teachers towards teacher stress.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between Above 15 years, and Below 15 years teaching experience towards teacher stress.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between Government School Teachers and Private school Teachers towards teacher stress.

Analysis of Data:

Gender vs Teacher Stress:

To test the validity of the above hypothesis, the following calculations are made. The table showing the significant differences between male and female teachers in respect of teacher stress.

Table - 1

Sex	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ Value
Male	85	28.41	6.02	1.54
Female	115	29.78	6.33	NS

From the above table 1, the calculated ‘t’ value is 1.54 found to be less than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level. Hence, the hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there is no significance difference between male and female teacher towards teacher stress.

Age vs Teacher Stress:

To test the validity of the above hypothesis, the following calculations are made. Table showing the significant difference between above 35 years age of teachers and below 35 years age of teacher in respect of teachers stress.

Table - 2

Age	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ Value
Above 35 years	129	161.66	35.70	0.56
Below 35 years	71	158.87	29.49	NS

From the above table 2, the calculated ‘t’ value is 0.56 found to be less than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level. Hence, the hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there is no significance difference between above 35 years age of teachers and below 35 years age of teachers towards teacher stress.

Educational Qualification vs Teacher Stress:

To test the validity of the above hypothesis, the following calculations are made. The table showing the significant differences between graduate teachers and post-graduate teachers in respect of teacher stress.

Table - 3

Educational Qualification	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ Value
Graduate Teachers	92	164.22	37.00	1.386
Post Graduate Teachers	108	157.63	30.20	NS

From the above table 3, the calculated ‘t’ value is 1.386 found to be less than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level. Hence, the hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there no is significance difference between graduate teacher and post-graduate teachers towards teacher stress.

Management vs Teacher Stress:

To test the validity of the above hypothesis, the following calculations are made. The table showing the significant differences between govt. school teachers and private school teachers towards in respect of teacher stress.

Table - 4

Type of Management	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ Value
Government Teachers	91	161.67	32.47	0.419
Private Teachers	108	159.68	34.76	NS

From the above table 4, the calculated ‘t’ value is 0.419 found to be less than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level. Hence, the hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there is no significance difference between govt. school teachers and private school teachers towards teacher stress.

Teaching Experience vs Teacher Stress:

To test the validity of the above hypothesis, the following calculations are made. The table showing the significant differences between teaching experience of above 15 years and below 15 years towards in respect of teacher stress.

Table - 5

Teaching Experience	N	Mean	SD	't' Value
Above 15 years	92	159.78	36.488	0.344
Below 15 years	108	161.42	31.044	NS

From the above table 5, the calculated 't' value is 0.344 found to be less than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level. Hence, the hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there is no significance difference between experience of above 15 years and below 15 years towards teacher stress.

Findings of the Study:

- ✓ There is no significance difference between Male and Female school teachers towards teacher stress.
- ✓ There is no significance difference between Above 35 year's age of school teachers and below 35 years age of school teachers towards teacher stress.
- ✓ There is no significance difference between Graduate teachers and Post-Graduate teachers towards teacher stress.
- ✓ There is no significance difference between Govt. school teachers and private school teachers towards teacher stress.
- ✓ There is no significance difference between Experience of above 15 years and below 15 years towards teacher stress.

Suggestions:

A stress management programme in the Indian setting may combine some elements of Gita and Yoga in the preventive plans. Srivastava (1981) concluded that persons coping more effectively with stress have more positive orientation to life in general, and employ a valuable mix of coping and defense response. Yoga is a holistic science, which gives to the person tools and techniques to expand conscious awareness into the unconscious In order to become aware of the patterns and tendencies that cause stress.

- ✓ The stress creators harm the teacher effectiveness and teaching competency
- ✓ The government or Private management of the institution should improve the conditions for better teaching by reducing the stress factors.
- ✓ The main stress creators like lack of promotional opportunities lack of professional growth are to be tackled to improve the teaching competency.
- ✓ Unless stress creators are reduced qualitative improvement teaching, learning process cannot be improved.

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